

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses important sources about the Timurid family tree. Historical events by the author year after year (Although the historical data in the source are covered in a periodic sequence, a number of historical data are repeated in the text, in some cases the periodic sequence of months and days being overlooked by the author. This situation makes it necessary to study similar historical data in comparison with other written sources.

KEYWORDS: important sources, Timurids family tree, historical events, historical data, periodic sequence, text, comparison, genealogical information, personographic information.

INTRODUCTION

A number of written sources on the history of the East, created in the XIV-XVI centuries, contain a lot of genealogical and personographic information about the life of Timuri mirza and princesses. Among these sources is the Mujmali Fasihi, which chronicles historical events from the creation of the world to 845 / 1441-1442 AH. Written in Persian by Fasih Ahmad ibn Jalaliddin Muhammad al-Hawafi, this chronicle-specific source consists of a preface, an introduction, two articles, and an introduction. The main part of the work deals with the history of the Timurids, after giving information about the Arab caliphs, Saffarids, Samanids, Ghaznavids, Seljuks, Guris, Khorezmshahs [1.12-13]. Historical events by the author year after year (Although the historical data in the source are covered in a periodic sequence, a number of historical data are repeated in the text, in some cases the periodic sequence of months and days being overlooked by the author. This situation makes it necessary to study similar historical data in comparison with other written sources. (Comment by A. Bakiev, in the following lines A. B.), illuminated in a periodic sequence, the source contains a large amount of informational material. The source of "Mujmali Fasihi" has been attracting the attention of orientalists since the middle of the XIX century. Including B.A.Dorn, A.Berge, V.R.Rozen, E.G.Braun, Ch.A.Stori, V.V.Bartold, I. P.Petrushevskiy, H. Raverti, Abulhay Habibiy, Ali Akbar Dexhudo, A. M. Belenitskiy, A. Urinbaev, Sadri Afshar, Muhammad Taqiy Donish Pajukh, Huseyn Kariman, I. Imronov, Ja'far Shiar , A. I. Falina , M. Farrux , D.Yu. Yusupova , B. Ahmedov , T. Fayziev , the research of H. Sattori and others is an example of this [2.8-12]. In this study, "Mujmali Fasihiy" [1.346]. Information about the Timurid family tree YOMITX [3.41-62] attempting to analyze. The chronological period of the Timurid family tree in the source covers the years 736-845 / 1336-1442 AH. In determining the information boundary (layer) of genealogical data, it is important to determine the number of Timurid princes and princesses whose names are mentioned in the source.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Table 1 below shows the names of the Timurid mirzas in the Mujmali Fasihi arranged according to the order of the meeting (Amir Muhammad Taragay, the patriarch of Amir Temur, Amir Temur, the founder of the dynasty, and the mirzas (mirak) who belonged to the Temurids on their mother's side should be included in the table).

№	Timuri mirzas	page	The degree of kinship of the mirzas to the Timurids and other dynasties	Page
1	Amirzoda Amironshah Bakhodir	59-60	1) Son of Amir Sahibkiran Temur Koragon 2) the father of Prince Khalil Sultan 3) The father of Prince Abu Bakr 4) Grandfather of Prince Ilongir ibn Abu Bakr 5) Grandfather of Prince Usman Jodi ibn Abu Bakr 6) Father of Prince Umar 7) Prince Iyjal's father	59-60 127 128 128 128 128 128

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

			8) Prince Suyurgatmish's father	128
			9) Spouse of Princess Khanzoda	141
			10) Father of Princess Aga Begi	172
2	Amir Sahibkiran Amir Temur Koragon	60	1) Amir Taragay ibn Barqal ibn Ilangiri Ijil ibn Qarajar noyan ibn Suqu Sijan ibn Irimkhai ibn Qojulay noyan ibn Tumanaykhan ibn Baysungur khan ibn Qaydukhan ibn Dutam ibn Mannan ibn Buka ibn Budanjir ibn Alan Tava khatun; 2) Amir Taragay Muhammad ibn Barqal ibn Ilangir ibn Ijil ibn Qarajar noyan ibn Suqu Seyjan ibn Irdamji ibn Qojulay noyan ibn Tuminay khan ibn Boysunqur khan ibn Qaydukhan ibn Dutum Mannon ibn Buka ibn Budanjir ibn Alanquva-khatun; 3) Father of Princess Sultan Bakhti Begim 4) Son-in-law: Amir Suleiman the Magnificent ibn Amir Dawud duglat	60 96 114 114
3	Amir Muhammad Taragay	60	Father of Amir Sahibkiran Temur Koragon	60
4	1) Amirzoda Jahongir 2) Amirzoda Muhammad Jahongir	97 98	1) Son of Amir Sahibkiran Temur Keragon 2) Wife: Xonzoda 3) Father of Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan	98 98 101
5	Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan	101	1) The son of Amirzoda Jahangir ibn Amir Sahibkiran Amir Temur Keragon 2) the father of Prince Jahangir 3) the father of Prince Sa'd Waqqas 4) the father of Prince Yakhyo 5) Father of Princess Oga Begi 6) Grandfather of Princess Khanzoda begim	101 128 128 128 184 184
6	1) Shohrukh Bakhodirkhan 2) Shohrukh sultan	101 110	1) The son of Amir Sahibkiran Amir Temur Keragon 2) The father of Giyosiddin Boysungur Bahodirkhan 3) The father of Ghiasiddin Muhammad Joki 4) The father of John the Oglan 5) The father of Muhammad Yari	116 119 123 128 128
7	Prince Khalil Sultan Bakhodir	111	1) Prince Amironshah's son 2) Spouse of Princess Shodmulk khotun 3) Son of Princess Khanzoda	127 145 163
8	Amirzoda Umarshaykh Bakhodir	113	1) Son of Amir Temur Koragon 2) Spouse of Princess Sevinch Kutlug agon 3) the father of Amir Pir Muhammad 4) the father of Prince Rustam 5) Grandfather of Umar Shaykh ibn Pir Muhammad 6) the father of Prince Alexander 7) Ahmad's father 8) Sayyid Ahmad's father 9) Boykaro's father	114 117 117 117 128 128 128 128 128
9	1) Amirzoda Pir Muhammad 2) Amirzoda Pir Muhammad Kabuli	115 202	1) Son of Amirzoda Jahangir 2) Kaidu's father 3) Khalid's father 4) The father of Buzanjir 5) Father of Sa'd Waqqas 6) Sanjar's father 7) The father of Caesar 8) Jahangir's father	115 128 128 128 128 128 128 128
10	Mahdumzoda Muhammad	117	1) The son of "Sultan Shahrukh Bakhodirkhan ibn Amir	117

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

	Taragay Ulugbek		Sahibkiran Amir Temur Koragon	
11	Amirzoda Pir Muhammad	117	1) Son of Amirzoda Umarshaikh Bakhodir	117 128
12	Amirzoda Ibrahim Sultan (The author, while writing about the birth of Mirza Ibrahim Sultan, referred to him as deceased. So, at the time of writing, this mirza had died (A.B).	117	1) Son of Shahrukh Bakhodir Khan	117
13	Amirzoda Rustam	117	1) Son of Amirzoda Umarshaikh Bakhodir 2) Osman's father 3) Father of Sultan Ali	117 128 128
14	Giyosiddin Boysungur Bahodir Khan	119	1) Son of Shahrukh Bakhodir Sultan	119
15	Amirzoda Iskandar	119	1) Son of Amirzoda Umarshaikh Bakhodir	128
16	Mahdumzoda Ghiyosiddin Muhammad Joki Bakhodir	123	1) Son of Shahrukh Bahodir Khan	123
17	Amirzoda Sultan Hussein (Although the name of Sultan Hussein is mentioned several times in the text of the source, the author does not mention his belonging to the Timurids and the degree of kinship, although he was from his mother. It is possible that this was due to the fact that Shahrukh Bahodir Khan and those close to him had a negative attitude towards this prince (A.B).	122		
18	1) Amirzoda Jahongir 2) Amirzoda Muhammad Jahongir	128 154	1) The eldest son of Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan	128
19	Amirzoda Sa'd Vaqqos	128	1) The middle son of Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan	128
20	Amirzoda Yahyo	128	1) The youngest son of Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan	128
21	Kaydu	128	1) The eldest son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
22	Khalid	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
23	Buzanjir	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
24	Sa'd Vaqqas	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
25	Amirzoda Sanjar	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
26	Amirzoda Qaysar	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
27	Jahongir	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir	128
28	Umarshayx	128	1) Prince Pir Muhammad ibn Umarshaikh's son	128
29	Usmon	128	1) The eldest son of Amirzoda Rustam	128
30	Sultan Ali	128	1) The youngest son of Amirzoda Rustam	128
31	1) Ahmad 2) Sayyid Ahmad Mirak 3) Amirzoda Ahmad Mirak	128 140 153	1) Son of Amirzoda Umarshaikh Bakhodir	128
32	Saydi Ahmad	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Umarshaikh Bakhodir	128

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

33	Boyqaro	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Umarshaikh Bakhodir	128
34	Abu Bakr	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Amironshah Koragon 2) Brother of Amirzoda Umar	128 129
35	Ilongir	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Abu Bakr	128
36	Osman Jodi	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Abu Bakr	128
37	Amirzoda Umar	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Amironshah bakhodir	128
38	Iyjal	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Amironshah bakhodir	128
39	Suyurgatmish	128	1) Son of Amirzoda Amironshah bakhodir	128
40	Suyurgatmish	128	1) Son of Shahrukh Bakhodirkhan	128
41	John Oglan	128	1) Son of Shahrukh Bakhodirkhan	128
42	Muhammad Yori	128	1) Son of Shahrukh Bakhodirkhan	128
43	An unnamed prince	136	1) Son of Amir Suleiman Shah (mother - Sultan Bakht Beg)	136
44	An unnamed prince	168	1) Son of Amirzoda Ahmad Mirak	168
45	An unnamed prince	169	1) Son of Prince Iskandar ibn Prince Umarshaikh	169
46	Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan (Fasih Hawafi allowed confusion here. As mentioned in the text, Amir Muhammad Sultan, whose name is mentioned in the text, is not the grandson of Amir Sahibkiran Amir Timur Keragon, but the son of Amir Muhammad Muhammad Jahangir ibn Amir Muhammad Sultan ibn Amir Muhammad Muhammad Jahongir (A.B).	175	1) The son of Amirzoda Muhammad Jahangir ibn Amir Sahibkiran Temur Koragon	175
47	Amirzoda Pir Ali	175	1) The son of Amirzoda Iskandar ibn Umarshaykh Bakhodir	175
48	Mahdumzoda Ruknuddin Alouddavla Ahmad bakhadir	179	1) Son of Boysungur Bahodir ibn Shahrukh Bakhodir 2) Spouse of Beka sultan binti Jaloliddin Yodgorshah arlot	179 207
49	Mahdumzoda amirzoda Ibodullah	179	1) Son of "Sultan Ulugbek Koragon	179
50	Mahdumzoda Sultan Muhammad	183	1) Son of Amirzoda Boysungur Bakhodirkhan	183
51	Sultan Abu Ishaq	184	1) Son of Sultanzoda Ibrahim Sultan ibn Shahrukh Bakhodirkhan	184
52	Amirzoda Abdulloh	190	1) Son of Sultan Ulugbek	190
53	Mahdumzoda Abdurrahmon	192	1) Son of Sultan Ulugbek Koragon	192
54	Amirzoda Abulqosim	194	1) Son of Sultan Boysungur Bahodirkhan	194
55	Amirzoda Muhammad Qasim	194	1) Son of Sultan Ghiyosiddin Muhammad Joki Bakhodir	194
56	Amirzoda Ali	195	1) Son of Mahdumzoda Giyosiddin Muhammad Joki Bakhodir	195
57	Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan	195	1) Son of Amirzoda Muhammad Jahangir ibn Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan ibn Amirzoda Jahangir Bakhodir	195
58	Mahdumzoda Muizzuddin Abu Bakr	202	1) Son of Prince Ghiyosiddin Muhammad Joki Bakhodir	202
59	Amirzoda Muzaffar	203	1) Son of Amirzoda Boykaro	203
60	Amirzoda Ismail	207	1) Son of Amirzoda Ibrahim Sultan	207
61	Amirzoda Abdulloh	208	1) Son of Amirzoda Ibrahim Sultan	208

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

62	Mahdumzoda Abulkhoris Boysungur Bakhodirhon	211	1) The son of Sultan Ruknuddin Alouddavla Bakhodir ibn as-Sultan Boysungur Bakhodirkhan ibn Shahrukh Bakhodirkhan	211
63	Prince Muhammad Bakr	212	1) Son of Amirzoda Khalil Sultan ibn Amiranshah Koragon	212
64	Mahdumzoda Abdullatif Bakhodir	215	1) Son of Sultan Ulugbek Koragon	215
65	Prince Imoduddin Sultan Masud	216	1) The son of Nosiriddin Suyurgatmish Bahodir ibn Sultan Shahrukh Bahodirkhan	216
66	Prince Muhammad Ibrahim	218	1) Son of Sultan Ruknuddin Alouddawla	218
67	Amirzoda Qorachar	218	1) Son of Prince Suyurgatmish Bakhodir	218
68	Bobur sultan	222	1) In the narration of the events after the fourteenth month of Shawwal 845 / 1441-1442 (25.02.1442), the Great Hakan, believing the false accusations of some slanderers, reported that Babur Sultan and the great Hajj Ghiyasuddin Pir Ahmad ibn Hajj Ishaq al-Khawafi were angry. Mentioned (Fasih Hawafi did not specify the identity of Babur Sultan, whose name is mentioned in the text. Given that the epitaph "Sultan" was mainly applied to members of the ruling class, it is possible that this person was a Timurid mirza. To determine the identity of this historical figure, it is expedient to make a genealogical systematic analysis of other primary sources that reflect the events of that period (A.B.).	222
69	Amirzoda Jaloluddin [4.111]	222	1) Send of Amir Bahadur, arrested by Amirzoda Jaloluddin, to Sulaymaniyah fortress on Tuesday (16.03.1442) on the third of the month of Dhu'l-Qa'dah 845 / 1441-1442	222
70	Amirzoda Rustam Bakhodir [5.222]	222		

Table 2. Below is compiled in the order in which the names of the Timurid princesses appear in the Mujmali Fasihi:

№	Timurid princesses	Page	The degree of kinship of the princesses to the Timurids and other dynasties	Page
1	Princess Xonzoda	97	1) The wife of Amirzoda Jahangir 2) The wife of Amirzoda Amironshah 3) Mother of Amirzoda Khalil Sultan Bahodir 4) Daughter of Khorezmshah Hussein Sufi	97 141 163 163
2	Princess Dilshod aga	99	1) The wife of Amir Temur	99
3	Princess Tumon aga	101	1) The wife of Amir Temur	101
4	Kutlug Turkon aga	108	1) Sister of Amir Sahibkiran Amir Temur	108
5	Princess Saray Mulk khanim	111	1) The wife of Amir Temur	111
6	Malika Sultan Baxt Begim	114	1) Daughter of Amir Temur Koragon 2) The wife of Sulaymanshah ibn Amir Dawud Duglat 3) The mother of an unnamed princess 4) The mother of an unnamed prince (mirak) 5) Mother-in-law of Abdussamad Amir Haji Sayfuddin	114 114 136 136 136
7	Princess Sevinch Kutlug aga	114	1) The wife of Amirzoda Umarshaikh the hero	114
8	Malika Bekasi sultan	119	1) The wife of Alexander the Great	119
9	Princess Tokal khanum	120	1) The wife of Amir Temur 2) Daughter of Hizrkhojahan	120 120

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

10	An unnamed princess	133	1) The wife of Amirzadeh Abu Bakr 2) Daughter of Tokal Orus Buqon	133 133
11	An unnamed princess	136	1) Daughter of Amir Suleiman Shah 2) Daughter of Princess Sultan Bakhti Beg 3) The wife of Abdussamad Amir Haji Sayfuddin 4) Mother of Sheikh Yasavul 5) Yusuf Qurchi's mother 6) Mother of Doro	136 136 169 169 169 169
12	Princess Shodmulik khatun	145	1) The wife of Amirzoda Khalil Sultan	145
13	Malika Khonum	154	1) The wife of Ghiyasiddin Muhammad Joki 2) Daughter of Amir Idiku	154 154
14	Princess Gavharshod aga	163	1) The wife of the great Haqqan Shahrukh Mirza	
15	Malika Hasiba Sultan Khanzoda begim	165	1) The daughter of Sultan Ulugbek Keregon	165
16	Princess Maryam Sultan	166	1) The wife of Amirzoda Muhammad Jahangir ibn Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan 2) Daughter of the great Hakan Shahrukh	166 166
17	Princess Ago Begi	172	1) The wife of Amirzadeh Sa'd Waqqas ibn Amirzadeh Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir 2) Daughter of Amirzoda Amironshah	172 172
18	Princess Mehri Nigor	183	1) The grandson of Hizrkhojahan 2) Daughter of Sham'i Jahon 3) The wife of Ghiyosiddin Muhammad Jokin	183 183 183
19	Princess Oga Begi	184	1) Daughter of Prince Muhammad Sultan ibn Prince Jahangir 2) The mother of Khonzoda begim	184 184
20	"Princess Xonzoda begim"	184	1) Daughter of Malika Oga Begi bint amirzoda Muhammad sultan	184
21	An unnamed princess	190-191	1) The wife of Prince Khalilullah Darbandi 2) Daughter of Amirzoda Abu Bakr Bahodir	190-191 191
22	Princess Ruh Parvar aga	196	1) The wife of Amir Temur 2) The wife of Hamza Sulduz 3) The wife of Amir Ali Tarkhan 4) The wife of Amir Hasan Sufi tarkhan	196 196 196 196
23	Princess Beka Sultan	208	1) Daughter of Amir Jaloluddin Yodgorshah arlot 2) The wife of Rukniddin Alouddavla sultan	208 208
24	Princess Ruqiya Sultan beka	210	1) The wife of Amirzoda Muhammad Sultan ibn Amirzoda Muhammad Jahangir 2) Sultanzoda Suyurgatmish ibn Sultan Shahrukh Bahodirkhan's daughter	210 210
25	An unnamed princess	214	1) The harem of Prince Giyasiddin Joki 2) Daughter of Qara Osman	214 214
26	Princess Oyisha Begika	216	1) The wife of Prince Imadiddin Sultan Mas'ud ibn Nasir al-Din Suyurgatmish 2) Daughter of Shahzoda Boysungur Bahodirkhan	216 216
27	Princess Milkat aga	220	1) Daughter of Hizr oglan	220

In the source there is a lot of genealogical and personographic information about the life of Timurid mirza and princesses in the form of chronological categories. We consider it expedient to divide this information into the following types according to their content and essence:

- Information on the dates of birth of Timurid mirza and princesses;
- Information on the number of children of Timurid mirzas;
- Information about the age of Timurid mirza and princesses;
- Information on celebrations, circumcision, engagement and weddings dedicated to the birth of Timuri mirzas;

An Important Source About the Timurid Tree

- Information on celebrations, engagements and weddings dedicated to the birth of Timurid princesses;
- Information about the negative events in the lives of Timurid mirza and princesses;
- Information on the political activities of Timuri mirzas;
- Information about the military activities of Timuri mirzas;
- Information about the struggle of the Timurid mirzas for the throne with each other and with other political forces;
- Information about the creative activities of Timurid mirza and princesses;
- Information about the departure of Timurid mirzas to the village (winter);
- Information about the outbreak of Timurid mirzas;
- Information about the hunting of Timurid mirzas;
- Information about the ascension of Timurid mirzas;
- Information that the Timurid mirzas visited the tombs of famous saints and prophets;
- Information about Timurid mirzas who were imprisoned, arrested or otherwise punished;
- Information on the dates of death (execution, death, etc.) of Timurid mirza and princesses;
- Other types of information.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the analysis of the genealogical data of the Timurid princes and princesses in the source by type, the Mujmal-i Fasihi developed. As a result of the study, the first phase of a three-step systematic analysis will be carried out at YOMIXT. As a result of categorizing the information in the primary written sources of the Timurid period, it is possible to compare them with each other.

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